

Date:

Patient card

Patient numer	
First name	
Surname	
Birth date	

PESEL number <small>(Polish Universal Electronic System for Registration of the Population)</small>														
---	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Interview

Question	Answer	Additional comment
Male Age (y)		
Female Age (y)		
Diagnosed or suspected female factor of infertility?		
Time of trying for offspring		
Biological fatherhood, if yes, age of childe		
History of infertility treatment including failure		
History of pregnancy loss		
Libido self-assessment		
History of erectile dysfunction		
History of genital injuries		
History of cryptorchidism		
History of varicocele		
History of urogenital infections		
History of chronic diseases		
History of pharmacotherapy		
History of anabolic steroids		
History of operations and treatments		

History of exposure to harmful factors (including smoking and lifestyle factors)		
History of others factors that could affect fertility		

Physical medical examination

Parameter	Description/results
Overall body assessment (including body and hair proportions)	
Penis palpation	
Gonads palpation	
Epididymides palpation	
Seminal cords palpation	
Inguinal canal palpation	
Prostate palpation	
Mammary glands palpation	

Ultrasonography examination

Structure	Description/results
Gonads <small>Testes volume (length × width × height × 0.71)</small>	
Epididymides	
Seminal cords <small>Including varicocele and blood flow</small>	
Other	

Reproductive hormones assessment

Hormone	Results	Additional comment
FSH		μIU/mL
LH		uIU/mL
PRL		ng/mL
TSH		μIU/mL
total T		nmol/L

FSH – follicle-stimulating hormone, LH – luteinizing hormone, PRL – prolactin, TSH – thyroid-stimulating hormone, total T – total testosterone.

Additional comments/results:

Recommendations for the patient:

Diagnosis:

ICD code:

Date and signature